

Studies on the Reactions of Oxotetrahalomolybdates (V)

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Pyridinium Oxotetrabromomolybdate (V), $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOBr}_4]$, has been synthesised as bright red shining crystals. Ethanolysis of the compound yields an oxobridged dimer, of the composition $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\text{OH})_2\text{Br}_4\text{Py}_2]$. Infrared and electronic spectra of the pyridinium salt have been studied and its structure discussed.

RECENTLY Saha and his coworkers¹⁻³ have made systematic investigations on the properties of oxopentahalomolybdates (V). It has been clearly noted by them that the chemistry of quinquevalent molybdenum is mainly dominated by the oxomolybdenum cations like MoO^{5+} , $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_3^{4+}$ and $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4^{2+}$, the stabilities of which are mainly dependent on the acidity of the solution. This is of interest to mention in this connection that the products of various reactions studied by them so far, mainly depend on the nature of both the base 'R' and the halogen 'X' in $\text{RH}_2[\text{MoOX}_5]$.

While studying the possibilities of preparing the oxotetrahalomolybdates (V) by the method of Saha and Benerjee⁴ we found that if pyridine hydrobromide is added to the cold hydrobromic acid solution obtained by the reduction of molybdenum trioxide with concentrated hydrobromic acid yellowish green crystalline $(\text{pyH})_2[\text{MoOBr}_6]$ is obtained. But if this solid dipyridinium oxopentabromo-molybdate (V) is boiled with excess hydrobromic acid and cooled to room temperature, bright red shining crystals of the composition $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOBr}_4]$ are obtained. The same compound can be directly obtained also by adding the pyridinium hydrobromide to the hot hydrobromic acid solution of quinquevalent molybdenum described already. When green dipyridinium oxopentabromomolybdate (V) is allowed to stay in a lime desiccator, then also red crystals of $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOBr}_4]$ are obtained within a week. This pyridinium oxotetrabromomolybdate (V) on boiling with ethanol yielded a copper-red crystalline solid which is diamagnetic and non-electrolytic in nature. Analytical data correspond to the composition of $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\text{OH})_2\text{Br}_4\text{py}_2]$. It is interesting to note that this oxotetrabromomolybdate (V) could not be prepared in the case of salts of other bases like α -picoline, piperidine, 2, 2'-bipyridyl and 1, 10-phenanthroline. Moreover, the corresponding chloro compound $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOCl}_4]$ also could not be prepared. The salt $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOBr}_4]$ and its derivative $[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\text{OH})_2\text{Br}_4\text{Py}_2]$ have been characterised by analytical data and other physicochemical investigations.

Experimental

All reagents used were of A. R. grade.

Analysis: Molybdenum¹ and bromide were estimated gravimetrically as MoO_3 and AgBr respectively and nitrogen was estimated by Dumas' method. Oxidation state of the metal was determined by ceric sulphate method.

Preparation

Pyridinium Oxotetrabromomolybdate (V) $\text{PyH}[\text{MoOBr}_4]$: A sample of 2g of molybdenum trioxide was boiled with 15 ml of 48% hydrobromic acid and the solution was concentrated to a pasty mass. The process was repeated again with a fresh 10 ml of the same hydrobromic acid. Finally, the residue was dissolved in 15 ml of hydrobromic acid and the solution was heated to boiling. This was added to a solution of 2 ml pyridine previously acidified with hydrobromic acid and the mixture was again boiled. On cooling to room temperature bright red shining crystalline solid began to separate. This was filtered in a sintered gooch X'ble and finally dried to constant weight in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH. Yield 4g.

Found. Mo, 18.76% ; Br, 62.09%, N, 3.03%

Calcd. for $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}[\text{MoOBr}_4]$. Mo, 18.75%, Br, 62.73, N, 2.73. Oxidation state of the metal was determined by ceric sulphate method and was found to be 4.96.

Oxo- μ -dihydroxobromo (pyridine) molybdenum (V)

About 2g of pyridinium oxo-tetrabromo-molybdate (V) were boiled with 15 ml of dehydrated ethanol 2-3 mins and the soln. was cooled to room temperature. Copper-red crystalline solid separated out which was filtered in a gooch crucible and dried in a vacuum desiccator over solid KOH to constant weight. Yield 1g.

Found Mo, 25.87%, Br, 43.11%, N, 3.72%

Calcd. for $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\text{OH})_2\text{Br}_4(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})_2$, Mo, 26.05%, Br, 43.42% and C, 3.79%. Oxidation state of the metal was found to be 4.94.

Conductance measurement: Conductance measurements were made in aqueous solution in a 'dip type' conductivity cell and the values of molar conductance at different dilutions indicate that both these compounds are extensively hydrolysed and ionised in aqueous solutions.

Magnetic susceptibility: Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made in Guoy balance with a field strength of 8500 gauss and the magnetic moment was worked out by the formula, $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.839 \sqrt{\chi_M \cdot T}$ where χ_M = corrected molar magnetic susceptibility = $\chi_M + \chi_d$ (χ_M = uncorrected value and χ_d = diamagnetic correction for ligands) and T = absolute temperature. The values ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.68$ B. M. for the salt and for the derivative) indicate that the salt fairly agrees with the "spin only" value for d^1 configuration of quinquevalent molybdenum whereas, the diamagnetism indicates a metal-metal interaction in the oxo bridged derivative.

I. R. Spectra: Infrared spectra were taken in Perkin Elmer infra-red spectrophotometer in KBr pellets. The main bands are given in Table 1. From infra-red spectra molybdenum-oxygen stretching frequency $\nu_{\text{Mo-O}}$ may be located at 975 and 970 cm^{-1} in case of these compounds¹. The bands in the region 700-800 cm^{-1} may be due to chain vibration of oxobridged compound.

Fig. 1. Electronic spectra of pyridinium oxotetrabromomolybdate (V) $\text{PyH} [\text{MoOBr}_4]$ in acetonitrile.

Discussion

Both these compounds $\text{PyH} [\text{MoOBr}_4]$ and its derivative $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\text{OH})_2\text{Br}_4\text{py}_2$ are well-characterised.

TABLE 1

Compounds	Infra-red bands in cm^{-1}						
$\text{PyH} [\text{MoOBr}_4]$	655m,	720 vw,	740m,	865m,	975m,	1225 vw,	1470m, 1510m, 1585m
$\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_2(\text{OH})_2\text{Br}_4\text{Py}_2$	715s,	790s,	880vw,	970vs,	1050vw,	1150 vw,	1200vw, 1500m, 1700m, 3200 bsh

m = medium, vw = very weak, s = strong, vs = very strong, bsh = broad shoulder

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRUM OF $\text{PyH} [\text{MoOBr}_4]$ IN ACETONITRILE

Compound	λ_{max} in μ	ν ($\text{cm}^{-1} \times 10^{-3}$)	Molar Extinction ϵ	Assignment
$\text{PyH} [\text{MoOBr}_4]$	760	13.15	13	${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}$ (I)
	500	20.00	150	${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_1$
	420	23.8	160	${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}$ (II)
	318	31.45	116000	${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_2$ (I)
	273	36.63	1,77,000	${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_2$ (II)
	250	40.00	1,97,000	${}^2\text{B}_2 \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}$ (III)

Electronic spectrum: Electronic spectrum of the salt was taken in acetonitrile in the Hilger UVISPEK, the results are plotted in Fig. 1 and the assignment² is given in Table 2. The oxobridged species decomposes slowly in aqueous solution and is insoluble in other common organic solvents, hence its spectrum could not be taken.

The tetrabromoderivative presents interesting problem due to the apparent co-ordination and unsaturation of the metal atom which seems to be pentacoordinated. In view of the paramagnetism and identical electronic spectra² of this compound with the $[\text{MoOBr}_5]^{2-}$ ion it seems probable that in the solid state it is a bromo-bridged dimer rather than the oxobridged compound,

because, the latter is diamagnetic¹⁻². The larger bromine atoms will set Mo atoms sufficiently apart to remove the possibility of Mo-Mo interaction leading to diamagnetism which is very common in oxobridged dimer.

References

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